

Finding Provenance, Finding Purpose:
An Analysis of the Skeleton on Page 41 of
Parasurama Shastri's 1931 Edition of the *Sarngadhara Samhita*

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Introduction

Seminal western medical and anatomical texts such as *De Fabrica Corporis Humani* from 1543 by Andreas Vesalius and the mid nineteenth century's *Gray's Anatomy* by Henry Gray are replete with etchings that were highly detailed and thus incredibly didactic. Conversely, Āyurvedic medical compendiums from Classical India, such as the *Caraka* and *Śusruta Samhitās*, and later treatises such as the fourteenth century *Śārṅgadhara Samhitā* had no images of the body in an anatomical sense, or any images of a medical nature.¹ However, in 1931 an intriguing edition of the *Śārṅgadhara Samhitā* edited by Parasurama Shastri and published in Bombay, India came to the fore.

What makes this particular edition worthy of interest is the employment of anatomical engravings of Western origin, specifically that of a skeleton found on page 41.² While this is not the first example of 'Western' anatomical imagery found in an Āyurvedic text during this period, Dominik Wujastyk argues that as the text makes no reference to this image, it is solely iconographic.³ What is also interesting is that there is no source listed for this particular image. What was the purpose of this image? Moreover, where did it originate from?

¹ Dominik Wujastyk, *The Roots of Ayurveda: Selections from Sanskrit Medical Writings*. Rev. ed. (London: Penguin, 2003), 225; Dominik Wujastyk, "Interpreting the Image, of the Human Body in Premodern India," *International Journal of Hindu Studies* 13 no. 2 (2009): 207. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11407-009-9077-0>

² Pandit Sarṅgahdaracharya, *The Sarṅgahdara Samhita* edited by Pandit Parasurama Shastri 2nd ed. (Bombay: Nirnaya Sagar, 1931), 41.

³ Wujastyk, "Interpreting the Image," 217-218. There are other compendiums and texts that included Western engravings of anatomical and physiological functions into illustrate the processes of the body. See Gananath Sen's *Pratyaksasariram* (1913-22) as example.

In light of these questions, I will discuss my analysis of this skeleton as well as my findings on the provenance. I will also present hypotheses as to how this particular ‘Western’ anatomical image appeared in this treatise in India. Preceding this analysis, I will provide a concise discussion on the history of medical imagery and Ayurvedic texts to shed light on how this synthesis came to pass. The intent of this discussion is to give deeper context and meaning to the analysis of my findings of the the Shastri skeleton on page 41 of the *Sarnagdhara Samhita*.

Medical Imagery in Āyurvedic Texts: A Brief History

The lack of anatomical imagery in the early Āyurvedic texts could arguably be due to the way *vaidyas* (Āyurvedic practitioners) viewed the human body. Āyurvedic medicine is primarily concerned with pathology as illustrated by systems of balance through three humors or *dosas*: *kapha* (phlegm), *pitta* (bile) and *vata* (wind).⁴ At its most basic level, when these humors are not in balance disease is imminent.⁵ Anatomy was still arguably an integral part of Āyurvedic medicine by way of surgery, as indicated by the *Susruta Samhita*.⁶ However, the body is found to be separated into categories within Āyurvedic anatomy, and thus is vastly different from how the

⁴ David C. Tabor, “Ripe and Unripe: Concepts of Health and Sickness in Ayurvedic Medicine,” *Social Science & Medicine Part B Medical Anthropology* 15, (January 1981) 442. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-7987\(81\)90019-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-7987(81)90019-3)

⁵ Hans Zimmermann, “The Conception of the Body in Āyurvedic Medicine: Humoral Theory and Perception,” *Ecole des Hautes Etudes en Sciences Sociales Rev. ed.* 2005, online: <https://www.slideshare.net/elsavonlicy/the-conception-of-the-body-in-ayurvedic-medicine>, 2-4; Wujastyk, “Interpreting the Image,” 205. For a comprehensive description of Āyurvedic medicine please see Wujastyk’s *Roots of Ayurveda: Selections from Sanskrit Medical Writings*, Rev. ed. (London: Penguin Books, 2003): xvii-xxii.

⁶ Wujastyk, *Roots*, 65-70.

body is approached in modern Western anatomy; these two views are not homologous in that they are rooted in two different epistemological approaches to medical investigation.⁷

The lack of images in the early Āyurvedic texts do raise questions as they would have had their didactic purposes. Perhaps illustrations were precluded due to the high level of description found within the *Caraka* and *Susruta Samhitas*. It has been suggested that mnemonic devices found in *Caraka* were created to facilitate the memorization process.⁸ It has also been argued that Caraka himself was not the original author of this text; his was an edition of a previous compendium, which raises questions as to how old this particular tradition is, perhaps predating the invention of writing in India.⁹ As India has a strong history of oral traditions, perhaps medical practices were initially an oral tradition prior to the arrival of the written word. Further, it would have been necessary for oral recounts of medical practices to be highly detailed in order to teach medical procedures accurately. Thus it stands to reason that when the medical practices were finally written down, the level of descriptive detail negated the need for didactic imagery. This argument may also explain why the treatises are so highly detailed, and perhaps shed light on the purpose of the idiosyncratic aspects of the texts.¹⁰ Perhaps these idiosyncrasies were a kind of synesthetic device for image-making to help facilitate memorization.

Anatomical illustrations remained more or less absent within Āyurvedic editions until the late nineteenth century.¹¹ It was at this time when a concerted effort was made by the British via

⁷ See Wujastyk, *Roots*, 270-274; Wujastyk, "Interpeting the Image," 205.

⁸ Wujastyk, *Roots*, 8.

⁹ Wujastyk, *Roots*, 4.

¹⁰ Such as the curds reference that has no context, see Wujastyk, *Roots*, 8.

¹¹ Wujastyk, "Interpreting the Image," 212.

the Calcutta Native Medicine Institute and Sanskrit College to ‘convert’ *vaidyas* to the more ‘advanced’ European medical practices as seen by the British.¹² However, these programs were shut down and replaced by an exclusively Western medical curriculum taught only in English, thus solidifying the impression that Western medicine was perceived as superior over the indigenous medicine practiced by the *vaidyas*.¹³

However, *vaidyas* such as Kariraj Gangadhara Roy continued the legacy of Āyurvedic medicine in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, by establishing Āyurvedic medical schools or *tols*.¹⁴ This endeavour was responsible in part for the preservation of India’s traditional medicine, which led to a kind of ‘renaissance’.¹⁵ This revival, in conjunction with the dominating Western medicine likely prompted some editors to inject Western anatomical imagery into traditional Ayurvedic texts as a response. As Wujastyk argues, this brought about a kind of marriage between both the ‘traditional’ and ‘Western’ medical worldviews.¹⁶ Perhaps these images were an attempt to legitimize and modernize Āyurveda in the eyes of the British. Attempts to ‘modernize’ a medical system forced in part a kind of professionalism in effort to

¹² Brahmananda Gupta, “Evolution of Ayurveda Through the Ages,” in *History of Medicine in India: The Medical Encounter*, eds. Chittabarata Palit and Achintya Kumar Dutta (Delhi: Kalpaz Publications, 2005), 214-15.

¹³ Gupta, “Evolutions,” 215; David Arnold, *Science, Technology and Medicine in Colonial India* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2000), 62-63; Zhaleh Khaleeli, “Harmony or Hegemony? The Rise and Fall of the Native Medical Institution, Calcutta: 1822-35,” *South Asia Research* 21 no. 1 (2001), 83.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/026272800102100104>

¹⁴ Gupta, “Evolution,” 216.

¹⁵ Subrata Pahari, “Travails of Traditional Medicine,” in *History of Medicine in India: The Medical Encounter*, eds. Chittabarata Palit and Achintya Kumar Dutta (Delhi: Kalpaz Publications, 2005), 226-27.

¹⁶ Wujastyk, “Interpreting the Image,” 212-13.

compete against such a dominating medical worldview.¹⁷ It stands to reason that this demand for ‘professionalism’ could be related to the adoption of Western medical iconography.

This attempt at an epistemological synthesis is strongly represented in the Shastri edition of the *Sarngadhara Samhita*. Based on the arguments presented above, the use of Western medical imagery in this edition was an attempt to legitimize this text in the eyes of Western medical practitioners. What is puzzling however, is the lack of reference of the text to the image. Moreover, this specific skeleton is clearly not as sophisticated as ones found in other treatises. While Western in origin, it is not an actual anatomical illustration.

The Shastri Skeleton Findings

The Shastri Skeleton presents as a Western anatomical engraving from what appears to be the 19th century (*figure 1*). Posed in an elegant position, this male skeleton displays articulations of the bones, specifically that of the ulna and radius of the right arm in a kind of homage to the images found in Vesalius’s *De Fabrica* (*figure 2*). However, the skeleton in the *Śārṅgadhara* is almost closed off by the position of this left arm, thus not providing a full display of the details such as the articulations in the hands and the aforementioned forearm. These visual limitations suggest that this particular ‘medical body’ was not meant for complex anatomical analysis.

Gray’s Anatomy for example present the human skeleton in sections providing a more erudite treatment of anatomy, thus allowing for deeper examination. Indian texts such as Gananath Sen’s anatomical treatise *Pratjaksasarian* (1913-22) shows a complete human skeleton which is clearly

¹⁷ Charles Leslie, “The Modernization of Asian Medical Systems,” in *Rethinking Modernization: Anthropological Perspectives*, eds. John J. Poggie Jr. and Robert N Lynch (Westport Conn: Greenwood Press, 1974) 100-01.

intended for medical purposes.¹⁸ Moreover, the treatment of the engraving is more sophisticated and refined, a hallmark of intentional attention to the necessary details needed for the study of human anatomy (*figure 3*). The *Śārṅgadhara* skeleton however, is simply iconographic in design, and not necessarily for medical analysis. This is evident via the left ulna and radius whose rotation is difficult to decipher due to the heavy treatment of the image via intaglio.¹⁹ What is curious about this image is the diagrammatic lines which do not include any references. Perhaps this was an attempt to interpolate ‘anatomical importance’ of the image via the usage of referential lines. However, failing to provide any referential material arguably brings the authority of the image (and the editor) into question.

Figure 1, Shastri Skeleton: Pandit Sarṅgadhara, *The Sarṅgadhara Samhita* edited by Pandit Parasurama Shastri 2nd ed. (Bombay: Nirnaya Sagar, 1931), 41.

¹⁸ Gananath Sen, *Pratyaksha Shariram: A Textbook of Human Anatomy in Sanskrit Part I* 3rd ed. (Calcutta: Kalpataru Ayurvedic Works, 1924), 14.

¹⁹ The quality of the image may also have been affected by the inking or printing process.

Figure 2, Andreas Vesalius, *De Humani Corporis Fabrica libri septem* (Basel: Ex officina Joannis Oporini, 1543), 163. Historical Anatomies on the Web https://www.nlm.nih.gov/exhibition/historicalanatomies/vesalius_biblio.html (accessed February 25, 2018).

Figure 3, Gananath Sen, *Pratyaksha Shariram: A Textbook of Human Anatomy in Sanskrit Part I* 3rd ed. (Calcutta: Kalpataru Ayurvedic Works, 1924), 14. Image produced by Gwyneth Pheasant Lust.

As for the provenance of the skeleton of the 1931 edition of the *Śārṅgadhara*, two potential sources have been found.²⁰ The first source, found in *The Illustrated Natural History of the Animal Kingdom* by S. G. Goodrich which was published in New York in 1859.²¹ Upon closer examination it was clear that the skeleton from this text was not an exact match (*figure 4*). However, it did have characteristics that were similar to that of the *Śārṅgadhara* skeleton, such as the diagrammatic lines that indicated positions of certain bones and joints, as well as the positioning of the body. It is clear however, that these lines are not exact as noted by the angle difference between the two lines positioned above the cranium. Differences were also found between the vertebrates between the ribs and the pelvic girdle, as well as the shape of the skull and placement of the left hand upon the left femur.

A more qualifying image was found in a text by a Dr. Worthington Hooker, who was the chair of Theory and Practice of Medicine at the Medical College of Yale.²² This text, titled

²⁰ The search for these images was conducted on January 31, 2018 at my home using reverse imaging software available via Google under the search ‘19th century skeleton anatomy line engraving’. The image has been replicated many times, but I was able to locate an image that provided a source to the text by an American named S. G. Goodrich. After discovering that the image was not an exact match, I performed a second search, this time at the University of Alberta on February 2, 2018. The search results yielded different results than that at my home, likely due to the change in location. Using the same search parameters. I was able to find the source for the skeleton in Dr. Worthington Hooker’s *Natural History for the Use of Schools and Families*, who is also American. After close comparison, this skeleton was found to be a match.

²¹ Samuel G. Goodrich, *Illustrated Natural History of the Animal Kingdom, Being a Systematic and Popular Description of the Habits, Structure, and Classification of Animals from the Highest to the Lowest Forms, with their Relations to Agriculture, Commerce, Manufactures, and the Arts* (New York: Derby & Jackson, 1859), 32.

²² “Medicine Department of Yale College.” *New York Journal of Medicine* 5, no. 2 (November 1852), 437. *American Medicine, Surgery, Dentistry Periodicals, 1786-1877*, EBSCOhost (accessed February 18, 2018)

Natural History for the Use of Schools and Families was published in 1864, also in New York.²³

The skeleton found on page 14 is in a very similar position to that of the Goodrich skeleton (figure 5). The treatment of the Hooker skeleton in terms of engraving is remarkably similar to that of the *Śārngadhara* skeleton. Moreover, the vertebrate and hand are in the exact same position. Curiously, the diagrammatic labelling is not similar. Whereas the Goodrich skeleton has long diagrammatic lines, the Hooker skeleton has only short lines. What is important to note however, is that the engravings originate from neither an anatomical or medical text, but that of natural history. Therefore the intention of these engravings were not to represent the body anatomically in a medical setting.

Figure 4, Samuel G. Goodrich, *Illustrated Natural History of the Animal Kingdom, Being a Systematic and Popular Description of the Habits, Structure, and Classification of Animals from the Highest to the Lowest Forms, with their Relations to Agriculture, Commerce, Manufactures, and the Arts* (New York: Derby & Jackson, 1859), 32.

²³ Worthington Hooker, *Natural History for the Use of Schools and Families* (New York: Harper & Brothers, 1864),

Figure 5, Worthington Hooker, *Natural History for the Use of Schools and Families* (New York: Harper & Brothers, 1864), 14.

While the similarities between both the Goodrich and Hooker engravings in relation to the *Śārṅgadhara* skeleton are extraordinary, the origins of these texts are even more compelling. How did American texts come to circulate in Bombay, let alone India during the early twentieth century? It would make for a more logical conclusion that the engraving found in the *Śārṅgadhara Samhita* were from a European text (e.g. British) rather than an American one.²⁴ However, there is a small potential connection between the Hooker text and India. Elihu Yale (1649-1721) who was a British merchant and worked within the British East India Company in Madras around 1670 was also one of the main benefactors of Yale College.²⁵ Hooker, as

²⁴ Another intriguing find was that of the stomach found on page 43 of the *Śārṅgadhara Samhita* which I had found using the same method for the skeleton. The image used may have come from a French encyclopedia titled *Nouveau Dictionnaire Encyclopédique Universel Illustré: Répertoire des Connaissances Humaines vol. 2* (p. 647) by Jules Troussel, 1885. There is also a possibility that the lungs on page 58 of the *Sarngadhara* comes from a French text. <https://www.granger.com/results.asp?image=0065321&itemw=4&itemf=0001&itemstep=1&itemx=17>

²⁵ 2017. "Elihu Yale" in the *Columbia Electronic Encyclopedia*, 6th Edition 1. *Literary Reference Centre*, EBSCOhost (accessed February 18, 2018).

mentioned, was the Yale medical college chair in 1852. While there is nearly 200 years between these two men, this institutional connection may provide some explanation as to how a text by a Yale medical chairman was able to make its way over to India. Another possibility as to how these engravings made their way into India is perhaps they originated from Europe and made their way to the United States. It would be much easier for these engravings to travel from Europe to India and perhaps it is only by happenstance that these same engravings appear in texts from the United States. Unfortunately the Goodrich and Hooker texts do not give credit to the authority of the engravings, and thus make this difficult to ascertain. While further investigation into this line of inquiry is beyond the scope of this paper, scholarship of this nature may uncover a deeper and more complex understanding of how this Western medical icon made its way into the Shastri edition of the *Sarngadhara Samhitā*.

Conclusion

In light of the discovery of the potential provenance of the Shastri skeleton, questions are raised as to where Western medical images that started to surface in Ayurvedic texts originate from. As indicated by the research, the possibility of overseas images arriving in Ayurvedic texts complicate and deepen these investigations. Further, the lack of reference between text and image raise questions pertaining to the purpose of the usage of these images. While there are more questions than answers, the examination and results of this particular image may yield more scholarship into the provenance and purpose of ‘Western’ medical images found in Āyurvedic texts, as well as expand the search for connections between Western medicine and Ayurvedic medicine outside of British colonial rule.

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